

Rationalizing Irrational Markets - Don't Let FUD Control Your Investments

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

While Bitcoin is the most recognizable, there are more than 1,500 current cryptocurrencies available. We are a few years away from real adoption. Price fluctuations are nothing compared to the long term vision and bigger picture. I wanted to share my knowledge and experience on crypto investing.

2. Aim

Global adoption is a common goal, but to get there we need to do a better job of educating the mass audience.

3. Materials & Methods

This is the golden list of rules I set in place for myself that I look for when investing into ICOs and cryptocurrencies:

1. INVEST ONLY WHAT YOU CAN AFFORD TO LOSE - Set long term and short term goals.
2. Read the whitepaper - Does the business model make sense? Look at the token economy, the distribution and use of tokens.
3. Does the project have an existing and working product that solves a real world problem?
4. Look at the team & advisors - What skill sets and experience does each member have?
5. Is there a road map - Has the team delivered and executed timelines?
6. Look at the market cap - How much is the team trying to raise?
7. Milestones - Look at partnerships in place, agreements, PR, and marketing.
8. Community - How large, knowledgeable, and supportive are the admins and community? Look at the social media channels.
9. DO YOUR OWN RESEARCH - Surround yourself with people who are smarter than you - Join blockchain communities and ask questions.
10. Add value to the community of projects you believe in - Write articles, create videos, welcome and educate newcomers, and correct misinformation spread by others with sources.
11. Do not trust media and headlines (FUD & FOMO) - Media is uneducated in the space

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and as you've seen has caused people to panic. Do not trust random links, unfamiliar emails, and social accounts on any platforms - There are several scams. Protect your accounts, back-up all of your private keys, and get a hardware wallet.

12. Remember why you got into crypto in the first place.

13. BE PATIENT - The end result will be rewarding. We are part of a movement that will change history forever. The market is emotional - If you truly believe in the projects you invested in, stick to your gut.

4. Results

It's simple. Do your research, be patient, ignore the noise, and trust your gut in the blockchain projects you truly believe will shape and change the future.

5. Keywords

Cryptocurrencies, Blockchain, Token Sale, Investing, Speculation, ICOs, Regulation, Education, Women, Whitepapers, Community, Roadmaps, FUD, FOMO, HODL, Disruption, Research, Market, Volatile.

Author biography

Jacqueline Kim Perez One of the women helping lead Vancouver's rise to prominence in the global Blockchain

industry, Jacqueline is an entrepreneur, crypto-enthusiast, and the Program Manager of Victory

Square Technologies and Blockchain Assembly. She has extensive experience in the technology

sector with expertise in blockchain, cryptocurrencies, public companies, sales, marketing, event

planning and management. She is a huge proponent of blockchain technology and believes it will

transform the global market, change the way we transact value, and streamline a host of industries by facilitating trust and transparency between entities.